

**THE AFROFUTURE MAGICAL REALISM TROPE AS A TOOL
FOR BLACK FEMALE SELF ASSERTION IN NNEDI
OKORAFOR'S AKATA WITCH**

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Abstract

Black identity and culture over the years reechoes in the literary circle as a discourse that demands serious investigation. Right from his first contact with the white man in his home and subsequently in the New World, the black man's identity has always been brought to question. Redeeming his identity and culture and asserting same without the hegemonic epitaph of the racial white has been an engaging business for the black man. This paper entitled "The Afrofuture Magical Realism Trope as a Tool for Black Female Self Assertion in Nnedi Okorafor's *Akata Witch*" interrogates the place of magical realism in the assertion of the black man's identity, impartation of moral and cognitive values in the children as well as the maintenance of global order. Magical realism as an Afrofuture trope pays attention to the African myth and black science or sorcery as it is utilized in literature. In current times, one of the prominent theories that help in this kind of discourse is Mark Dery's theory of Afrofuturism with its emphasis on the re-imagining of the African past, present and future. Through the utilization of this theoretical parameter and the content analysis research methodology, this paper reveals that the devilish normative belief about the institution of African witchcraft and sorcery is here deconstructed. That which was viewed as barbaric and evil is imbued with virtues to be desired.

Keywords: Afrofuturism, Magical realism, Black female self-identity, black identity.

Résumé

Le trope du réalisme magique d'Afrofuturisme comme outil d'affirmation de soi chez les femmes noires dans Akata Witch de Nnedi Okoroafor

L'identité et la culture noires résonnent, au fil des années, dans le cercle littéraire comme un discours exigeant une enquête sérieuse. Dès son premier contact avec l'homme blanc chez lui et après dans le Nouveau Monde, l'identité de l'homme noir a toujours été remise en question. Racheter son identité et sa culture et les affirmer sans l'épithète hégémonique du blanc raciste a été une affaire engageante pour l'homme noir. Cet article intitulé «Le trope du réalisme magique d'Afrofuturisme comme outil d'affirmation de soi chez les femmes noires dans Akata Witch de Nnedi Okoroafor» interroge la place du réalisme magique dans l'affirmation de l'identité noire, l'impartition des valeurs morales et cognitives chez les enfants ainsi que le maintien de l'ordre dans le monde. Le réalisme magique en tant que trope d'Afrofuturisme prête attention au mythe africain et à la science ou à la sorcellerie noire telle qu'elle est utilisée dans la littérature. À l'heure actuelle, l'une des théories les plus importantes qui aident dans ce type de discours est la théorie de l'afrofuturisme de Mark Dery, qui met l'accent sur la ré-imagination du passé, du présent et du futur de l'Afrique. Grâce à l'utilisation de ce paramètre théorique et de la méthodologie de recherche d'analyse de contenu, cet article révèle que la croyance normative diabolique sur l'institution de la sorcellerie et on fait déconstruire la sorcellerie africaine. Ce qui était considéré comme barbare et maléfique est devenu quelque chose avec des vertus à désirer.

Mots-clés : Afrofuturisme, Réalisme magique, Identité féminine noire, identité noire.

Introduction

One of the emerging genres in literature today is speculative fiction. This genre is basically interested in re-imagining the African past, present and future. This position is in tandem with

Myungsung Kim's in his work "Afrofuturism, Science Fiction, and the Reinvention of African American Culture". He notes that "Modern and contemporary African American writers employ science fiction in order to recast ideas on past, present, and future black culture." (i) Furthermore he elaborates that; "It (Afrofuturism) seeks to locate the presence of black culture within the contemporary techno-scientific world, contesting any claims of an essential relationship between human, nature, and technology in the formation of racial identity. The objective of Afrofuturism therefore sums to be the reinvention of the black culture in its past and futuristic potentials aided by technology and

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science. There are several other subgenres within this corpus which include African science fiction or Africanfuturism, Afrofuturism, apocalyptic and prophetic narrative, post-apocalyptic narrative, magical realism etc. These subgenres are sometimes referred to as tropes of speculative fiction. The agendum of this paper is to underscore Nnedi Okorafor's *Akata Witch* under the magical realism trope of this speculative fiction.

Magical realism is a trope of fictive narrative or speculative fiction that blends elements of magic and African myth and reality into the narrative. The demarcation between these subgenres is difficult to draw as there seem to be the overlap of elements in many of the genres. For example, there seems to be a difficulty drawing a dividing line between African science fiction or Africanfuturism, into which category our referential text falls into and Afrofuturism. Afrofuturism appears to be focused on the literature of the people of colour including Africans, Afrocaribbean, African Americans and people all over the world with genetic affinity to the black race. The narratives of these people that blend elements of technology, African magic, reality and the imaginative future is often categorized as Afrofuturism. How can we draw the demarcation given the shared experience of the black people the world over? The essay addresses speculative literature from the view point of Africanfuturism focusing on magical realism as a trope of Africanfuturism. African science fiction is the hybridity of modern world, African technological advancement and fantasy. In other words, it is the blend of current realities with what is very strange and difficult to believe within the current order of things. This of course is in line with the tenets of science fiction the world over. Lisa Yaszek notes; "By telling tales that merge Eurowestern and African ways of knowing the world, Afrofuturists prove SF luminary author C. Clark's famous claim that any sufficient advanced in technology is indistinguishable from magic" (66).

Afrofuturist writing became prominent in America in the 1960s with the works of scholars like George Schuyler (*Black No More*), Samuel Delany, Octavia Butler, Ishmael Reed, Colson Whitehead, Nalo Hopkinson, etc. However, some versions of this style could be traced as far back as the 19th century with the publication of Martin Delany's *Blake* or the *Huts of America* in 1857. Nevertheless, the term Afrofuturism was coined by Mark Dery in 1994.

African science fiction and the utilization of African magic and myth in the development of the plot structure of African text seem to have begun in Africa with the publication of Amos Tutuola's *The Palm Wine Drinkard* in 1952. Tutuola's novel was largely seen by Eurocentric reviewers as primitive, naïve, lazy and un-willed. The New Yorker's review notes that; "Tutuola was "being taken a great deal too seriously" as he is just a "natural storyteller" with a "lack of

inhibition" and an "uncorrupted innocence" whose text was not new to anyone who had been raised on "old-fashioned nursery literature." The reviewer concluded that American authors should not imitate Tutuola, as "it would be fatal for a writer with a richer literary inheritance." (Wikipedia). However, this novel which was underrated, seems to have a strong attraction for the West years after its publication.

In the drama genre or theatre generally, the movie *Black Panther* is patterned after the Afrofuture paradigm. The *Black Panther* is a movie that shows the advancement in black science and technology. The movie uses black magic and such travel devices like space travels, magical travels between the physical world and the spiritual world or the world of the dead as well as interstellar to advance the plot of the movie.

As observed earlier, Afrofuturism and Africanfuturism embrace the concept of hybridity. Hybridity is a concept coined by Homi K. Bhabha to account for the blend of cultures and identities. It is different from W. E. B. Du Bois' concept of "dual consciousness" even though it is a little related to it and also related to Stuart Hill's "New Ethnicities" and Paul Gilroy's "Black Atlantic". Each of these concepts mentioned above would be examined at length in the section entitled "magical realism and the trauma of the multiplicity of dual identity". Afrofuturism squarely locates around the identity of the black man. As a subgenre in the speculative fiction genre, it seeks to re-imagine the African story and culture in a new light. In other words, it seeks to bring into light that which was thought to be negative about Africa in order to actually imbue it with the inherent virtue. It is important to point out that magical realism seeks to re-imagine African magic and black science. For instance, the issue of witchcraft and sorcery in Africa was thought to be barbaric and devilish. Nnedi Okorafor's *Akata Witch* re-imagines this by showing that just like any good thing can be abused, African witchcraft and sorcery can also be abused but that does not make it in itself evil. She pleads this new paradigm by painting a character of Black Hat Otokoto who is a witch but decided to use it for evil. On the other hand, she also creates the characters of Anatov, Sugar Cream, Chichi, Sunny, Orlu, Sasha and other witches who through the same means contribute immensely to the peace of the world and mutual coexistence of the individuals in the world. In this text, she re-imagines it like the prophetic ministry of the Eurocentric Christian religion, which can be used for either good or bad purposes. This is the essential nature of sorcery in the African traditional religious belief system.

In analyzing the role of magical realism in addressing the trauma of dual identity in the text, the paper examines how magical realism helps Sunny in the formation

of her identity. Equally, the place of magical realism in the maintenance of order in the world will be discussed under the section titled: 'magical realism and emerging global order'. Finally, magical realism would be reviewed as a vehicle for the inculcation of cognitive and moral rectitude in teenagers.

Afrofuturism is an emerging literary idiom and theory that is interested in the search, definition, redefinition and re-imagining of the black identity and culture. The term was first coined by Mark Dery in 1994 but this does not in any way implicate that the discourse or the narratives that are patterned after the Afrofuture paradigms began at this point. Afrofuture narratives, some believe had been in existence as early as the 18th century. This re-imagining cuts across gender and ethnicity. So it is possible to talk about Afrofuture feminism where the discourse focuses on the re-imagining and deconstruction of the Afrofuture woman in terms of her biological make up, psychological and physiological make up. This kind of discourse features within the corpus of such Afrofuture strands like eugenics and genetic engineering. It is possible also to talk about Afrofuture Marxism where the emphasis is on the deconstruction of the paradigms of the Afrofuture class relationships in the society. Psychoanalytical Afrofuturism, post humanistic Afrofuturism are also possibilities where the emphasis is on the post apocalyptic realities and experiences etc. It is a subgenre of the speculative fiction.

The proponents of Afrofuturism include, Mark Dery, George Schuyler, Samuel Delany, Octavia Butler, Ishmael Reed, Colson Whitehead, Nalo Hopkinson, Martin Delany etc. The debate is of course ongoing as to the beginning of Afrofuturism. What seems to be the order currently is the classification of the different stages in the evolution of the theory. There is the classification in terms of science fiction which seems to be popular in the west. There is also Afrofuture narrative that is believed to have his root in the Afrofuture narrative emanating from the African Americans and spreading to the black people all over the globe.

The basic tenets of this theory include the creation of a better world and the concept of racial tolerance which seems to feature prominently in Stuart Hill's "*New Ethnicities*" and Paul Gilroy's "*Black Atlantic*". There is also the concept of deconstruction, of ideological paradigms or what might be termed ideological role reversal. Here what seems acceptable with the current realities is deconstructed and re-imagined. This ideological role reversal affects knowledge production greatly. Here the normative is deconstructed. This aspect features greatly in the movie, "*Black Panther*" where the black man's technological advancement surpasses that of the white man. There is also the melding of genres

in Afrofuturism. Here there is the possibility of the blend of historical narrative, science fiction, fantasy, magical realism, apocalypses etc within one narrative.

Synopsis of the text.

Akata Witch is written by Nnedi Okorafor and published in 2011. The narrative is broken in terms of the narrative technique of the text as it begins with the first person narrative point of view in the prologue and then continues with the third person omniscient narrator in the remaining part of the text using the twelve years old Sunny. It is an Afrofuturist text modelled after the magical realism and apocalyptic trope. Sunny is the protagonist who is controlled by the apocalyptic forces she envisions in the candle at the beginning of the novel. This is one of the devices utilized by the writer in the advancement of the novel's plot.

Sunny is an African American; born in America to Nigerian parents. She returns to Nigeria when she is nine years following her mother's plea. Her mother appears knowledgeable about something connected to Sunny's identity and her traditional status in the maintenance of order back home in Nigeria. Sunny is conflicted and describes herself thus:

My name is Sunny Nwazue and I confuse people....I was born in the city of New York. We're Igbo- that's an ethnic group from Nigeria- so I'm American and Igbo, I guess. You see why I confuse people? I'm Nigerian by blood, American by birth and Nigerian again because I leave here. (Prologue p. 5).

Sunny has a host of attributable descriptions and multiplicity of identities. She is albino, African American, a free agent, a mystic- leopard person with the ability to exist in the world of the spirit as well as the human or physical world simultaneously. The narrative opens with her watching the slowly burning candle. She is actually in love with candles and on this particular occasion, as she watches, she sees something that catches her attention. She sees the return of Ekwensu to the world. Ekwensu in the world of the novel is the devil who has the destruction of the entire world as his mission. This suggests impending doom on earth and implies that her mission is to prevent this apocalypse from occurring. The entire narrative revolves around this singular mission. The return of Ekwensu to the world is actually the evil activity of a corrupted witch in the name of Black Hat Otokoto- a serial killer who delights in killing children and ensuring the return of Ekwensu to the world. Sunny's mission therefore is to kill Black Hat Otokoto and ensure that his mission of bringing Ekwensu does not succeed. Ekwensu is what Satan is to the Christians. As such, the return of Ekwensu

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means the return of Satan to the world as its sole ruler. To help Sunny in this mission, she makes friends with other leopard children with unique abilities and they form an *Oha* coven that will fight Black Hat to a standstill.

They are taken through a series of training by the senior witches. Anotov is their coach who ensures that all of them have mentors. Senior witches like Kehinde, Taiwo, Sugar Cream, etc do not have the power to fight Black Hat Otokoto because the nature of his assault is against children and therefore must be addressed by children who are the subject of his attack. They however take time to train the children for this assignment.

In the long run, this coven is able to attack Black Hat and conquer him and successfully return Ekwensu to the spiritual world. This achievement seems to be the definitive parameters for Sunny because it is after this victory that she fully becomes aware of her identity. She is a free agent but inherited the spirit from her grandmother Ozoemmenam who was actually the teacher and mentor of Black Hat Otokoto before he became corrupt. Otokoto had actually killed Sunny's grandmother because of his love for wealth and power. At the end, Sunny continues in the spirit of ozo her grandmother likely to remain unmarried for the rest of her life. The children in the *oha* coven are praised for a successful mission by the senior witches. As the narrative ends, a deconstructive reader is possibly taken through the deconstruction process as the normative of the barbarism of African witchcraft and sorcery is upturned and the virtues therein highlighted.

Magical Realism and the Trauma of Multiplicity of Dual Identity

In the last section we tried to give the synopsis of the text. One of the issues that seem to hold the trajectory of events in the text as we saw in the synopsis is the quest for an identity. We saw how Sunny's identity is tied to her purpose and mission in life. The two seem to be two streams that converge at a point and flow together without any difference. The question of identity in literature cannot be overemphasized as literature mirrors life. Living life is all about executing the purpose one was created for. Literature enhances of social order and so it cannot therefore give a closed eye to identity which helps that??? (Check to recast for clarity). As Aboh Romanus notes: "The world over, writers have, through their artworks, shown that one of the overriding social functions of literature is the quest for identity construction, reconstruction and the enactment of ideologies."(2), *Akata Witch* is purely structured on this paradigm.

Nnedi Okorafor weaves her plot around the question of identity of the black race. Two members of the *Oha* coven, Sunny and Sasha are African Americans while the other two members, Orlu and Chichi are Africans. Some other characters are

Americans, Caribbean etc. The concept of racial identity and tolerance is here addressed. At the outset, there seems to be a misunderstanding between Africans represented by Chichi and Orlu and the African Americans. This conflict is resolved when both parties unite because they discovered their relationship as leopard people or initiates in the sorcery cult. The question of dual identity at this level is addressed through magical realism.

We had mentioned the concept of dual consciousness, black identity, hybridity and border lives as well as new ethnicities. We did not expand on these. We suspended them because we needed to address them in context in this section. The black man's identity has been a serious debate issue particularly when he is not in his home continent. In America, the black man had to struggle with operating in dual consciousness as an African and then American. W.E.B Du Bois remarks that:

... the Negro is a sort of seventh son, born with a veil, and gifted with second-sight in this American world, -- a world which yields him no true self-consciousness, but only lets him see himself through the revelation of the other world. It is a peculiar sensation, this double-consciousness, this sense of always looking at one's self through the eyes of others, of measuring one's soul by the tape of a world that looks on in amused contempt and pity. One ever feels this two-ness, -- an American, a Negro; two souls, two thoughts, two unreconciled strivings; two warring ideals in one dark body, whose dogged strength alone keeps it from being torn asunder. (615).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that the black man's identity has continuously been debated. He is forced to doubt his own definition of himself and made to accept the erroneous one foisted on him by the Eurocentric view point. In a search for the retention of his identity, he is forced to carry a dual consciousness or identity particularly in the American soil. At a point, he is compelled to accept an identity he is not ready to neither have nor understand. He is therefore left with the choice of striving and fighting to assert his identity. Again, Du bois observes:

The history of the American Negro is the history of this strife, -- this longing to attain self-conscious manhood, to merge his double self into a better and

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truer self. In this merging he wishes neither of the older selves to be lost. He would not Africanize America, for America has too much to teach the world and Africa. He would not bleach his Negro soul in a flood of white Americanism, for he knows that Negro blood has a message for the world. He simply wishes to make it possible for a man to be both a Negro and an American, without being cursed and spit upon by his fellows, without having the doors of Opportunity closed roughly in his face. (615).

In the above statement Du Bois describes the concept of duality of identity as it affects the African American. It is different from Homi Bhabha's notion of hybridity in the sense that he reposes two distinct identities; African and American. This dimension is seen in the character of Sunny who introduces herself as American and Nigerian. Beyond this duality Sunny's identity somewhat dovetails towards Stuart Hill's concept of New Ethnicities. New Ethnicities is a term coined by Stuart Hill, conceptually captures the black self and culture outside the normative space of geographical parameters. Under the New Ethnicities categorisation, the black self is represented in a Diasporic space carved out for blacks or people of colour from different parts of the world: Britain, America, Africa etc. these black nationals come together in a community and there exist together. However, a second phase of this cultural and identity emergence is the fact that this formed community is not controlled by the concept of blackness nor any shared experience of trauma or pain. The concept that seems to hold the cultural tapestry of this emergent community is hybridity. Hybridity is not *contaminus* (conterminous?) to Du Bois concept of double consciousness; rather it seems to tilt towards Homi Bhabha's concept of border lives. The different concept of multiplicity of identity seen in Sunny in terms of her albinism, African American status, leopard person, free agent and her ability to exist in the physical and spiritual world simultaneously is here highlighted. Her Sunny's ability to traverse these diversities helps her ultimately in the accomplishment of her stated purpose. Sunny's albinism has something to do with her magical powers and helps in defining her. This is detailed in the conversation between her and Chichi: "people say stuff about people like you. That you're all ghost, or a half and half, one foot in this world and one foot in another world...that you can... see things. "Sunny rolled her eyes. *Not this again*, she thought. *So cliché. Everyone thinks the old old lady, the hunchback, the crazy man, and the albino have magical evil powers.*" (p.4 chapter 2). In the lambs' world, she is referred to as Akata witch because of her African American

status. In the leopard world, she is segregated as a free agent and a child. This is because she did not inherit the sorcery spirit directly from her mother. In chapter five we are told:

A free agent is one who isn't privileged with even one pure leopard spiritual line from the survivors of the great attempt. She or he is a random of nature, a result of mixed-up and confused spiritual genetics. Free agents are the hardest to understand, predict or explain. Learning will not come easy to you. You are a leopard person only by the will of the supreme creator, and as we all know, she isn't very concerned with her own creation. After your initiation, make sure that someone is there to help you, for you will not be able to help yourself, so new the world will be to you and so fragile your ego. You're like an infant. You will be dumbfounded and disoriented.... (p.4 Chapter 5).

This is the ordeal Sunny faces so much that even after her initiation she is unable to get a mentor to help her. In fact, it is at the end of the novel that Sugar Cream finally consented to mentoring her. She therefore is responsible for her own enlightenment and preparation to accomplish her mission. Sunny is tasked with navigating plural identities in order to assert herself and accomplish her mission and purpose. She achieves this through the utilization of magical realism. To realize this Sunny has to first come to terms with the fact that she has both spiritual and physical essences. This is metaphorized in terms of her physical and spiritual face. Realizing the dynamics means a lot to her as it relates to her self-assertion and purpose accomplishment. In chapter five, the omniscient narrator notes this state of mind thus:

“By three A.M., Sunny was weeping. She didn't know what to do or how to stop it, and there was no one to turn to for help. Around four, her body started shifting. Her face would become her spirit face and then it would go back to normal. Then it would become her spirit face again. Once, when her spirit face came forward, she got up and looked at herself in the mirror. She nearly screamed. Then she just stared. It was her, but it felt as if it had its own separate identity, too.... She was scared, but

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she was excited, too.... Realizing what she was, was the beginning of something, all right... but it was also the end of something else". (chapter 5, p. 2, 4).

This discovery was the "the beginning" in actuality the struggle she would encounter navigating these two identities at this point when her parents remained unaware of her new identity. This new identity would require her going to spiritual meetings that many times are held at night. Given the kind of father she has, she knows that this is practically impossible. Therefore, to maintain these two identities, she relies on magical realism. She would have to read about the kind of magic that would help her in doing this. She found out one that helps her to leave her house without having to open doors. The magic helps her to pass through walls and be invisible to the physical eyes thus: "God, I hope they don't come in here. She went over to the locked door. Before she could wonder what to do next, she was yanked through the keyhole. The sensation was itchy and a little painful. She came out on the other side of the door. About twenty copper chittim loudly clinked at her feet. She froze. Everyone had to have heard the noise. No one came. She tried to pick up one of the chittim. Her hand passed through it." (chapter 6. p. 8). This is what is called travel device in Afrofuturism. This one is magical. There are others that are mediated by technology like space travel, interstellar etc.

In combating the segregation of her albinism and African Americanism, Sunny is forced to fight her friend Jibaku in school to end the continuous assault on her. She reveals her magical face or spirit face to the assailant and this ends the attack in the lamb's world. In the leopard world, this hurdle of being a free agent is a big mountain to climb if she is to achieve her mission. The dimension of this mountain is succinctly expressed by Anatov when he told her that:

In any case, you're what we call a free agent leopard person. You're in a leopard spirit line... somehow. It is not a blood thing. Leopard ability doesn't travel in the physical. Though blood is familiar with spirit. It may have been through your grandmother or she may have just been crazy, who knows. It's known to happen once in a while, but rarely. Most leopard people are like your friends here, born to two sorcerer parents – strong ancestor connections. They are the most powerful, usually, those born to one parent can't do much of anything

unless they have an especially expensive juju knife or something like that or if they come from an especially adept mother. It travels strongest from woman to child, since she's the one who has the closest spiritual bond with the developing fetus." (Chapter 3. p. 11).

Sunny's ability to perform tasks ends the attack and assault. In fact, she is the last among the coven members to earn a mentor. Other members are adopted by mentors as mentees but she only gets Sugar Cream as her mentor after her prowess in defeating Black Hat Otokoto and successfully returning Ekwensu to the spirit world. After the conquest, it is reported thus: "For several moments, Sunny and Sugar Cream looked into each other's eyes. Sunny held her breath but didn't look away. Then Sugar Cream pursed her lips and said, "You've proven yourself today in more ways than one," she said. She crossed her arms over her chest and nodded. "okay." Sunny grinned. She finally had a mentor." (p.6 chapter 20).

Magical Realism as a Vehicle for Imparting Cognitive and Moral Rectitude in Teenagers.

It is generally believed in the African social environment that children initiated into witchcraft and sorcery are generally insulting and silly. However, within the world of the novel, this is re-defined. One of the tenets of Afrofuturism is the concept of ideological role reversal and the deconstruction of the normative. Here, what seems unacceptable is re-imagined and re-interpreted. The above ideological normative position about children in sorcery is deconstructed as the children here are taught moral values like respect for elders, empathy for human beings, love and respect for one another, team work, boldness, courage, and acceptance of responsibilities. For instance, when the children were sent by Anatov, their coach to meet with Taiwo, there was a bird that ought to carry them to Taiwo's hut. They despised the creature and the writer implied that so long as they remained aloof they would remain unable to accomplish their mission. It took the intervention of Orlu for them to decipher the bird's behavior and subsequently undergo an attitudinal change; a didactic moment for the children. "“Ah is that what you want? ... You want what everyone wants: to be treated like a human being”. The bird threw its head back and squawked loudly” (Chapter 9, p.17). The lesson learnt is that all of God's creations are related and that mutual respect is essential for existential harmony. The children come to terms with an important fact i.e. that any injury inflicted on any natural entity has potential

spiral effect on others. Once they began treating the bird with respect, it allowed them to ride on its back and flew them up the hill to Taiwo's abode.

The ability to transcend the two worlds and the possession of magical powers demands a good heart otherwise the individual could become wicked using the magical power to revenge evil done to him or his loved ones. This is exactly what Sasha did. For him to be corrected, he was sent to Nigeria as a form of punishment for using the power to make people mad and putting masquerades on others. Sunny had the ability to hurt Jibaku and her group but for the intervention and advice of Orlu. Orlu believes that magical power should be used positively. He advises Sunny thus: ““Never use juju on Lambs for petty revenge, you'll find yourself standing before the Library council trying to defend your actions. You don't want that, trust me” (Chapter 8, p. 2). Sunny is punished for revealing her spiritual face to Jibaku for the purpose of threatening her never to look for her trouble again.

The moral value of respect for elders manifests when the children visited Kehinde. Sasha spoke harshly to him and was reprimanded. They were taught by Kehinde that when elders are speaking, they are not expected to banter words with them. The issue of pride and arrogance was also addressed among the children when they visited Taiwo. This, unlike the normative belief about children in this institution is a kind of re-imagining of sorcery. The children in this institution are better behaved than those in the world. Empathy for fellow humans manifests when Orlu revived the children that Black Hat Otokoto had captured and hypnotized to be used as sacrifice to bring Ekwensu. He brought them back to life and ensured their return to their parents. Team work, boldness and conquering fear, acceptance of responsibilities and challenges manifest when the children were told that their mission was to kill Black Hat Otokoto to ensure that Ekwensu does not return to the world. They were initially afraid, but their seniors encouraged them and told them that their success lay in team work and that four of them possessed diverse skills which could be harnessed to accomplish their mission. They followed the elders' directions and conquered. All these align appropriately with the tenet of role reversal in Afrofuturism.

Magical Realism and Emerging Global Order

One of the principles of Afrofuturism is non-segregation along racial lines. Even though central to Afrofuturism is the concept of the projection of the black identity, this projection is not against other races neither is it done for the sole interest of the black community but for the holistic interest of the world. In fact, the technology that is prevalent in Afrofuturism is intended for the benefit of all and sundry. Sunny even wonders why the knowledge in the leopard world is not

all dished out to all members of the community without them necessarily going through the process of initiation. For instance the return of Ekwensu does not spell doom for the black race only but the entire world. Through the utilization of magical realism, this apocalyptic world event is subverted and order is restored to the world. Also through the utilization of this power, the evil personality; Black Hat Otokoto is eradicated from the world and his serial killing of children is brought to a halt.

Generally, Okorafor's style is marked by the use of local colours like the use of dialect, predominantly Efik and the incorporation of excerpts from the secret books of these institutions. Such words include *mbakwa* which is a level in the Ekpe cult, *ndibu*, *ekpiri* initiation, *insibidi*, *ebett* etc. These words are basically used in the Ekpe cult and the sorcery institution and therefore show the versatility of the author in the subject matter. They lend the narrative the credibility of reality. Apart from the lexical choices, she adopts a method of incorporating excerpt from the secret books of some of this institution. Some of these books are believed to be owned only by initiates since they are not bought in the general market. Again she incorporates the insibidi writings into her work to lend some degree of credibility.

Conclusion

In this paper, we made attempt at a close reading of Nnnedi Okorafor's *Akata Witch* using the parameters of Afrofuturism. We were able to explore the origin of Afrofuturism as well as its major proponent. We also noted that Afrofuture paradigms exist in such movies as *Black Panther* and such early African novels as Amos Tutuola's *The Palmwine Drinkard*. We explored the utilization of magical realism in combating the trauma of multiplicity of identity and the assertion of self. What we discovered here is that through the use of magical powers, Sunny; the protagonist of the narrative was able to combat this trauma and then assert herself as well as accomplish her purpose on earth. We also looked at magical realism as a vehicle for the impartation of cognitive and moral values among the teenagers. We ended the interrogation with the place of magical realism in staying evil persons in the world as well as ensuring world or global order by subverting an impending apocalyptic world event. We therefore conclude that within the world of the novel, there is a total ideological reversal and deconstruction of the normative belief about the institution of African sorcery. However, this should not be mistaken with the real practice in the real world as the truth that is discovered during an aesthetic experience is entirely and distinctly different from the truth that science and mundane reality may present.

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